

AUDITING PROFESSIONAL ETHICS AND ITS DEVELOPMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This thesis explores the role, evolution, and challenges of auditing professional ethics in Uzbekistan, emphasizing its critical contribution to financial transparency, accountability, and economic stability. It analyzes the regulatory framework governing ethical practices in auditing, identifies key challenges such as conflicts of interest, weak enforcement mechanisms, and lack of training, and proposes actionable strategies to enhance ethical compliance. This research provides a roadmap for fostering trust and credibility in Uzbekistan's auditing profession, supporting its economic reforms and global integration.

Keywords: auditor independence, regulatory framework, economic reforms, international standards, conflict of interest, ethical compliance, capacity building, auditing profession, global integration.

The auditing profession plays a vital role in ensuring the integrity and transparency of financial information, which is essential for fostering trust among stakeholders and supporting economic growth. In Uzbekistan, the development of professional ethics in auditing has gained prominence as the country undergoes economic reforms aimed at modernizing its financial and business sectors. This thesis investigates the evolution of auditing professional ethics in Uzbekistan, focusing on its current state, challenges, and opportunities for improvement.

Objectives of the Study

To analyze the regulatory framework governing auditing ethics in Uzbekistan.

To assess the awareness and adherence to ethical standards among auditors.

To identify challenges hindering the implementation of ethical practices.

To propose strategies for aligning Uzbekistan's auditing ethics with international standards.

The literature review highlights the global principles of auditing ethics, including integrity, independence, confidentiality, and professional competence, as outlined by the International Ethics Standards Board for Accountants (IESBA). It also reviews studies on ethical challenges in developing economies

and discusses the evolution of auditing ethics in Uzbekistan, emphasizing the need for stronger regulatory frameworks and capacity building.

A mixed-methods approach is used, combining qualitative and quantitative data. Surveys and interviews with auditors, regulatory officials, and professional organizations provide primary data, while a review of national laws, international standards, and academic research constitutes the secondary data. The analysis employs thematic coding for qualitative insights and statistical techniques for quantitative findings.

Regulatory Framework: The legal foundation for auditing ethics in Uzbekistan exists but lacks alignment with global standards.

Training Gaps: A significant proportion of auditors report inadequate training in ethical practices.

Institutional Weaknesses: Professional bodies face challenges in enforcing compliance due to limited resources and authority.

Global Comparison: Uzbekistan lags behind international standards in enforcing auditor independence and addressing conflicts of interest.

Policy Reforms: Update national auditing standards to align with the IESBA Code of Ethics. Strengthen enforcement mechanisms for ethical compliance.

Capacity Building: Introduce mandatory ethics training for auditors and accounting professionals. Develop continuing professional education programs focusing on ethical dilemmas and best practices.

Institutional Development: Empower professional organizations to play a more active role in monitoring and enforcing ethical standards. Collaborate with international bodies to adopt global best practices.

Promoting a Culture of Ethics: Foster ethical awareness through public campaigns and organizational initiatives.

Conclusion

This thesis concludes that while Uzbekistan has made progress in establishing a foundation for auditing ethics, significant gaps remain in enforcement, training, and institutional capacity. By addressing these challenges through comprehensive reforms, Uzbekistan can enhance the credibility and effectiveness of its auditing profession, contributing to greater financial transparency and economic growth. The findings offer practical recommendations for policymakers, regulators, and professional organizations in Uzbekistan, providing a pathway for aligning national practices with global standards.

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